

TOURISM IN SOUTH KOREA AND CHINA

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ABSTRACT

In this article, I would like to focus on the role of tourism in Asian countries and developing countries. Tourism is developing year by year, so I would like to highlight the Asian countries that are at the peak of their development today, mainly China and South Korea. Tourism is beneficial to humanity in all respects, both health and science.

In today's world, tourism is progressing year by year in developed countries of Asia. Asian countries can be specialized in tourism like UAE, Malaysia, China, Thailand, Japan because lots of incomes are coming from this industry. Besides that, the majority of people are working in hotels, restaurants, tourism agency, historical museum and other places. South Korea is one of the most scientifically and technologically advanced countries. As you know, the Korean government has made almost all parts of the tourism industry technically feasible. Mankind is now living in the age of technology. Everything we do today is done through technology. For tourists, first of all, peace conditions and then the nature is important. South Korea possesses all opportunities in every section and tourists wish to see the discoveries of technologies. In a result, All of above things bring benefits to the government. In addition to this, The majority of the South Korean tourist industry is supported by domestic tourism. Thanks to the country's extensive network of trains and buses, most of

the country lies within a day's round trip of any major city. International tourists come primarily from nearby countries in Asia. Japan, China, Hong Kong and Taiwan together account for roughly 75% of the total number of international tourists. The Korean wave has brought increasing numbers of tourists from Southeast Asia and India. The Korea Tourism Organization (KTO) is targeting 100,000 arrivals from India in 2013. Travel and Tourism based on international expenditure directly contributed KRW 16.7 trillion to the South Korean GDP and directly supported 1.4 million jobs, this represented 5.3% of the total employment in the country (OECD). According to the scientists, leisure spending is 64% higher than business spending while domestic spending is only 10% higher than international spending. Korea is full of touristic places such as Seorak scenic tour, Seoraksan national park and others, are cool and historical. Seorak scenic tour located in east of Seoul, Gangwon-do is a charming region, filled with the beauty of nature. Popular destinations

include Sokcho, where you can enjoy delicious foods one after another and Gangneung, full of various experiences and fantastic sights to see. Gangwon-do has also received much attention due to the 2018 Olympic Winter Games that were held in Pyeongchang and other regions of Gangwon-do. There are a lot of amenities in this place and enjoy both the mountains and the sea, experience a new and unique landscape with the changing of the seasons. From my point of view, as Gangwon-do is a destination with so many sights to see and things to try. That's why I suggest abroad people to come to this touristic place. If I talk about tourism in China, China is on top of the list in tourism industry. China is both historic and modern country in the world. Tourism industry plays an important role in China owing to the fact that China has reformed every field such as hotels, restaurants, historic places and others. In a result, tourists never stop coming to China and the economy is increasing step by step. Since 2012, tourists from China have been the world's top spender in international tourism, leading global outbound travel. In 2016, the country accounted for 21% of the world's international tourism spending, or \$261 billion. One of the famous places is The Great Wall of China. For all sections of the

Great Wall near Beijing, the spring months (April to June) offer temperate weather and are great for climbing. In April to May, many trees begin to blossom, making this a particularly beautiful period to visit the Wall. Fall is also a nice time to visit, as temperatures are usually comfortable. October to early November are particularly picturesque, as the tree leaves on the mountains begin to change color. The winter months from December to February are cold and can be windy, but there are usually far fewer tourists on the Wall during these months. July and August are hot and humid, and thus not the best for long hikes. In addition, it's best to avoid hiking on the Wall after rain or snowfall because some parts can get very slippery. Apart from this touristic place, there are The Forbidden City, The Terracotta Army, The Summer Palace in Beijing in China. Besides that, the majority of tourists visit China in order to see giant Panda in Beijing. From my point of view, both China and South Korea have always held high positions in the world in terms of tourism industry. but they are also high in the field of science, but at the same time they preserve their culture, history, customs and traditions. We can see all this in their holidays, in their national costumes.

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